

Supplementary Materials

Supplementary figures

Fig. S1 Raw data of corallite sizes of colonial scleractinian corals ($n = 1302$) through time. Note that some data in ARTD and the CTD contain specimen-level corallite size ranges (i.e., minimum, and maximum values), and that mean corallite widths were calculated here for these specimens. Also note that some entries were taken from global taxonomic reviews, so the ages of the raw data represent the mean of the recorded minimum and maximum ages.

Fig. S2 Raw corallite sizes through time for colonial scleractinian genera a) *Calamophylliopsis*, b) *Cerienstella*, c) *Cladophyllia*, d) *Isastrea*, e) *Microsolena*, f) *Retiophyllia*, g) *Stylosmilia*, and h) *Thecosmilia*. The thick grey lines represent median values; the dashed lines represent mean values; the thin grey lines represent 1st and 3rd quantiles.

Fig. S3 Stratigraphic ranges of colonial scleractinian genera against their corallite sizes. Note that the y-axis is log-transformed; (Tr—Triassic, J—Jurassic, K—Cretaceous, Pg—Paleogene, Ng—Neogene).

Colonial corals

Occurrence-weighted analyses

Fig. S4 Generalized random walk (directional change) model expectation with 95% probability interval for occurrence-weighted mean corallite width of colonial scleractinian corals.

Fig. S5 Unbiased random walk (URW) model expectation with 95% probability interval for occurrence-weighted mean corallite width of colonial scleractinian corals.

Fig. S6 Stasis model expectation with 95% probability interval for occurrence-weighted mean corallite width of colonial scleractinian corals.

Fig. S7 Histograms showing the distribution of adequacy tests autocorrelation, length of runs, fixed variance, and net change of the stasis model for occurrence-weighted colonial scleractinian corals using 10 000 simulated data sets. The red dashed vertical lines indicate the values of the test statistic from the observed data.

Range-through analyses

Fig. S8 Trajectory of mean corallite width (mm) of colonial scleractinian coral genera over time for unweighted diversity-based means without family Mussidae. The dashed grey line is the linear regression line; (Tr—Triassic, J—Jurassic, K—Cretaceous, Pg—Paleogene, Ng—Neogene).

Fig. S9 Trajectory of unweighted diversity-based range-through minimum corallite width (mm) of colonial scleractinian genera over time. The points mark minimum corallite sizes in each stage; (Tr—Triassic, J—Jurassic, K—Cretaceous, Pg—Paleogene, Ng—Neogene).

Fig. S10 Trajectory of unweighted diversity-based range-through maximum corallite width (mm) of colonial scleractinian genera over time. The points mark the maximum corallite sizes in each stage; (Tr—Triassic, J—Jurassic, K—Cretaceous, Pg—Paleogene, Ng—Neogene).

Fig. S11 Generalized random walk (directional change) model expectation with 95% probability interval for unweighted diversity-based range-through corallite width means of colonial scleractinian corals.

Fig. S12 Unbiased random walk (URW) model expectation with 95% probability interval for unweighted diversity-based range-through corallite width means of colonial scleractinian corals.

Fig. S13 Stasis model expectation with 95% probability interval for unweighted diversity-based range-through corallite width means of colonial scleractinian corals.

Fig S14 Histograms showing the distribution of adequacy tests autocorrelation, length of runs, and fixed variance of the directional trend model (GRW) for unweighted diversity-based range-through corallite width means of colonial scleractinian corals using 10 000 simulated data sets. The red dashed vertical lines indicate the values of the test statistic from the observed data.

Fig. S15 Histograms showing the distribution of adequacy tests autocorrelation, length of runs, and fixed variance of the random walk model (URW) for unweighted diversity-based range-through corallite width means of colonial scleractinian corals using 10 000 simulated data sets. The red dashed vertical lines indicate the values of the test statistic from the observed data.

Fig. S16 Histograms showing the distribution of adequacy tests autocorrelation, length of runs, fixed variance, and net change of the stasis model for unweighted diversity-based range-through corallite width means of colonial scleractinian corals using 10 000 simulated data sets. The red dashed vertical lines indicate the values of the test statistic from the observed data.

Sampled-in-bin analyses

Fig. S17 Trajectory of unweighted diversity-based sampled-in-bin minimum corallite width (mm) of colonial scleractinian genera over time. The points mark minimum corallite sizes in each stage; (Tr—Triassic, J—Jurassic, K—Cretaceous, Pg—Paleogene, Ng—Neogene).

Fig. S18 Trajectory of unweighted diversity-based sampled-in-bin maximum corallite width (mm) of colonial scleractinian genera over time. The points mark the maximum corallite sizes in each stage; (Tr—Triassic, J—Jurassic, K—Cretaceous, Pg—Paleogene, Ng—Neogene).

Fig. S19 Generalized random walk (directional change) model expectation with 95% probability interval for unweighted diversity-based sampled-in-bin corallite width means of colonial scleractinian corals.

Fig. S20 Unbiased random walk (URW) model expectation with 95% probability interval for unweighted diversity-based sampled-in-bin corallite width means of colonial scleractinian corals.

Fig. S21 Stasis model expectation with 95% probability interval for unweighted diversity-based sampled-in-bin corallite width means of colonial scleractinian corals.

Fig. S22 Histograms showing the distribution of adequacy tests autocorrelation, length of runs, and fixed variance of the directional trend model (GRW) for unweighted diversity-based sampled-in-bin corallite width means of colonial scleractinian corals using 10 000 simulated data sets. The red dashed vertical lines indicate the values of the test statistic from the observed data.

Fig. S23 Histograms showing the distribution of adequacy tests autocorrelation, length of runs, and fixed variance of the random walk model (URW) for unweighted diversity-based sampled-in-bin corallite width means of colonial scleractinian corals using 10 000 simulated data sets. The red dashed vertical lines indicate the values of the test statistic from the observed data.

Fig. S24 Histograms showing the distribution of adequacy tests autocorrelation, length of runs, fixed variance, and net change of the stasis model for unweighted diversity-based sampled-in-bin corallite width means of colonial scleractinian corals using 10 000 simulated data sets. The red dashed vertical lines indicate the values of the test statistic from the observed data.

Solitary corals

Occurrence-weighted analyses

Fig.S25 Trajectory of minimum corallite width (mm) of occurrence-weighted solitary genera. The points mark minimum corallite sizes in each stage; (Tr—Triassic, J—Jurassic, K—Cretaceous, Pg—Paleogene, Ng—Neogene).

Fig. S26 Trajectory of maximum corallite width (mm) of occurrence-weighted solitary genera. The points mark minimum corallite sizes in each stage; (Tr—Triassic, J—Jurassic, K—Cretaceous, Pg—Paleogene, Ng—Neogene).

Fig. S27 Generalized random walk (directional change) model (GRW) expectation with 95% probability interval for occurrence-weighted mean corallite width of solitary scleractinian corals.

Fig. S28 Unbiased random walk (URW) model expectation with 95% probability interval for occurrence-weighted mean corallite width of solitary scleractinian corals.

Fig. S29 Stasis model expectation with 95% probability interval for occurrence-weighted mean corallite width of solitary scleractinian corals.

Fig S30 Histograms showing the distribution of adequacy tests autocorrelation, length of runs, and fixed variance of the directional trend model (GRW) for occurrence-weighted corallite size means of solitary scleractinian corals using 10 000 simulated data sets. The red dashed vertical lines indicate the values of the test statistic from the observed data.

Fig. S31 Histograms showing the distribution of adequacy tests autocorrelation, length of runs, and fixed variance of the random walk model (URW) for occurrence-weighted corallite size means of solitary scleractinian corals using 10 000 simulated data sets. The red dashed vertical lines indicate the values of the test statistic from the observed data.

Fig. S32 Histograms showing the distribution of adequacy tests autocorrelation, length of runs, fixed variance, and net change of the stasis model for occurrence-weighted corallite size means of solitary scleractinian corals using 10 000 simulated data sets. The red dashed vertical lines indicate the values of the test statistic from the observed data.

Fig. S33 Boxplots showing the paleolatitudinal distribution of colonial coral occurrences that contain corallite sizes at each geological stage. The thick line represents the overall median paleolatitude and the dashed lines represent 1st and 3rd quantiles.

Supplementary tables

Table S1. Time bins used in this study according to the (Gradstein et al. 2020) time scale, with each time interval corresponding to a stage in the geological time scale. The number of occurrences in each bin is given for colonial and solitary scleractinian corals with corallite size measurements.

Bin	Series	Stage	Age at base (ma)	Number of occurrences	
				<i>colonial</i>	<i>solitary</i>
54	Middle Triassic	Anisian	246.7	42	24
55	Middle Triassic	Ladinian	241.46	41	11
56	Upper Triassic	Carnian	237	218	81
57	Upper Triassic	Norian	227.3	639	141
58	Upper Triassic	Rhaetian	205.74	427	104
59	Lower Jurassic	Hettangian	201.36	54	33
60	Lower Jurassic	Sinemurian	199.46	27	47
61	Lower Jurassic	Pliensbachian	192.9	79	104
62	Lower Jurassic	Toarcian	184.2	18	30
63	Middle Jurassic	Aalenian	174.7	59	13
64	Middle Jurassic	Bajocian	170.9	503	44

65	Middle Jurassic	Bathonian	168.17	266	67
66	Middle Jurassic	Callovian	165.29	188	34
67	Upper Jurassic	Oxfordian	161.53	1851	106
68	Upper Jurassic	Kimmeridgian	154.78	999	117
69	Upper Jurassic	Tithonian	149.24	837	86
70	Lower Cretaceous	Berriasian	143.1	138	22
71	Lower Cretaceous	Valanginian	137.7	221	14
72	Lower Cretaceous	Hauterivian	132.6	173	10
73	Lower Cretaceous	Barremian	126.5	361	8
74	Lower Cretaceous	Aptian	121.4	761	59
75	Lower Cretaceous	Albian	113.2	223	168
76	Upper Cretaceous	Cenomanian	100.5	242	112
77	Upper Cretaceous	Turonian	93.9	45	38
78	Upper Cretaceous	Coniacian	89.39	60	16

79	Upper Cretaceous	Santonian	85.7	109	31
80	Upper cretaceous	Campanian	83.65	132	74
81	Upper Cretaceous	Maastrichtian	72.17	247	278
82	Paleocene	Danian	66.04	75	383
83	Paleocene	Selandian-Thantetian	59.24	136	129
84	Eocene	Ypresian	56	88	129
85	Eocene	Lutetian	48.07	79	77
86	Eocene	Bartonian	41.03	130	142
87	Eocene	Priabonian	37.71	328	173
88	Oligocene	Rupelian	33.9	354	46
89	Oligocene	Chattian	27.29	741	166
90	Miocene	Lower Miocene	23.04	1095	221
91	Miocene	Middle Miocene	15.99	558	307
92	Miocene	Upper Miocene	11.63	950	263
93	Pliocene	Pliocene	5.33	1394	215
94	Pleistocene	Pleistocene	2.59	6444	355
95	Holocene	Holocene	0.0117	1066	15

Table S2. Model fit estimates of the analysed time series for occurrence-weighted colonial coral families with more than 1000 occurrences. Models used are GRW (generalised random walk or directional change), URW (unbiased random walk), and stasis. Estimates of the best model(s) are marked in bold. AICc, Akaike information criteria; Δ AICc, the difference between the AICc and the minimum AICc. Results of the adequacy tests (autocorrelation, runs, and fixed variance) for the two analysed models - GRW and URW, and an additional net change test for the stasis model. The results of tests are given in p-values, where values greater than 0.05 (marked in bold) indicate that the specific test was passed (Voje 2018).

Family	Model	AICc	Δ AICc	Weight	Autocor.	Runs	Fixed variance	Net change
Acroporidae (n = 2171)	GRW	-4.6	2.3	0.2	0.6	0.3	0.8	NA
	URW	-6.9	0	0.7	0.1	0.1	0.03	NA
	Stasis	-1.1	5.8	0.04	0.01	0.1	0.1	0.5
Latomeandridae (n = 1088)	GRW	73.3	22.1	0	0.01	0.02	1	NA
	URW	70.7	19.5	0	0.2	0.7	0.7	NA
	Stasis	51.2	0	1	0.3	0.8	0.8	0.7
Merulinidae (n = 2056)	GRW	84.6	3.4	0.1	0.2	0.1	1	NA
	URW	82.1	0.9	0.4	0.1	0.2	0.03	NA
	Stasis	81.2	0	0.5	0.1	0.6	1	0.4
Poritidae (n = 3910)	GRW	0.9	0	0.8	0.4	0.3	0.9	NA
	URW	3.9	3	0.2	0.2	0.5	1	NA
	Stasis	34.6	33.7	0	0	0.001	0.4	0.1
Stylinidae (n = 1208)	GRW	-13.9	0	0.9	0.3	0.9	0.3	NA
	URW	-9.3	4.6	0.1	0.6	0.3	0.2	NA
	Stasis	3.7	17.6	0	0.1	0.02	0.6	0.4

References

Voje, K. L. 2018. Assessing adequacy of models of phyletic evolution in the fossil record. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution* 9(12):2402-2413.